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A symbolic constructivist approach to exploring the philosophy and values of engineering

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INTRODUCTION

The global challenges of the future require engineers to be more reflexive and aware of the diverse cultural values, perspectives and philosophies that impact engineering practice and education. Yet, for the most part, engineering problem solving is embedded in Western philosophy, which has dominated the modern world. How can engineers become more conscious of the diverse worldviews, values, philosophies and dynamics that drive decision-making in world of ever-increasing complexity? This paper describes a methodology founded in a symbolic constructivist research approach which originated in psychologically oriented fields such as Jungian analytical psychology. The method allows for nonconscious material to be made evident and provides a way of expressing emotions and experiences that are often tacit and difficult to verbalise. As a case study to illustrate the method we present here part of our research where we invited engineering educators to co-construct a symbolic representation of three worldviews – Western, Engineering and Australian Indigenous – using wooden blocks and plastic figures. Collectively we explored the possible meanings of the symbols and metaphors created. We offer the methodology as a tool for opening discussions, for exploring intersubjectively-created understanding, and for undertaking research on the philosophy, values and worldviews that underpin engineering, be they those that currently dominate engineering education or those that are inadequately represented.

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1 BACKGROUND

This project continues our research into issues underpinning the low numbers of Indigenous engineers and engineering students in Australia. According to 2011 Census data, Indigenous people make up around 0.13% of university qualified engineers, compared to 3% of the overall population. A major outcome of the project was the development of a model for guiding the embedding of the perspectives of Aboriginal students and communities into engineering curricula [1]. The model comprises five sections – *Start with a new philosophy; Explore engineering from three perspectives; Consider and validate ‘an’ Aboriginal perspective; Engaging Aboriginal community; and Tailor the learning environment.*

Our research has indicated that a major challenge to embedding Aboriginal perspectives in the engineering curriculum lies in the first stage of the model – ‘Start with a new philosophy’ [2]. Further, while motivations and values indicate that there is significant support for embedding Aboriginal (and other) perspectives, there is a very small base of knowledge and experience of Aboriginal knowledges and worldviews and how they may change engineering itself [3].

The aim of the research presented in this paper was to expand one section of the model – *Explore engineering from three perspectives* (see Figure 1). In order to integrate the knowledge, philosophy and values of different worldviews into the engineering curriculum there is a need to know how engineering educators understand and differentiate between worldviews – and in this case the worldviews from a Western, an Engineering and an Indigenous perspective. But firstly, we need to ask “What is a worldview, and why is it important?”

Figure 1. Bringing together three worldviews

1.1 What is a worldview?

The concept of worldviews has been described as the cognitive, perceptual and affective maps through which an individual interprets the world and interacts with it. These maps are developed throughout a person’s lifetime through socialisation and social interaction. They are encompassing and pervasive in both adherence and influence. Yet they are usually taken for granted unconsciously and uncritically as the way things are. It also has been suggested that in any society there is a dominant worldview that is held by most members of that society [4].

James Sire, in his book *Naming the Elephant: Worldview as a Concept* [5, p. 16], highlights “two characteristics of any worldview: its understanding of prime reality and its pretheoretical (intuitive) character”. He expands on this (p, 141) to define a world view as “... a commitment, a fundamental orientation of the heart, that can be expressed as a story or a set of presuppositions (assumptions which may be true, partially true or entirely false) which we hold (consciously or subconsciously, consistently or inconsistently) about the basic constitutions of reality, and that provides the foundation on which we live and move and have our being”.

For sociologist Karl Mannheim, worldviews are virtually unconscious phenomena, which are taken for granted and are the prime movers in thought and action. More importantly he emphasis that, “as long as one does not call his own position into question but regards it as absolute, while interpreting his opponents’ ideas as a mere function of the social positions they occupy, the decisive step forward has not been taken” [6].

A worldview then involves the mind, and more importantly, the heart. But more fundamentally, the essence of a worldview involves first and foremost what lies deep in the inner recesses of the human self (unconscious). Therefore any research method used to explore worldviews needs to take into account the social and collective development of worldviews, provide a means for unconscious narratives to emerge and allow for reflexivity. With this in mind, symbolic constructivism was used as the research method of choice.

2 METHOD

2.1 Symbolic constructivism

Symbolic constructivism has its origins in the works of psychologist Carl Jung, who in 1912 wrote *The Psychology of the Unconscious*, where he distinguished between direct thinking, which leads to coherent logical patterns, and symbolic thinking, which is image-based and controlled by the unconscious [7]. Research over the years has shown that symbolic thought is both embodied and emotional [8-10].

Central to symbolic constructivism is the concept of symbol, which designates something that seemingly has determinable, sign-like form(s), meaning(s), and use(s) and that acts as a gateway to other understandings [11].

Symbolic constructivism is emerging as a qualitative research approach that uses an art-based portrayal (which can include drawings, photographs, sculpture, dramatisation) to elicit, explore, challenge, and shift existing sense-making frameworks. In the 1990s LEGO® developed a methodology called LEGO® Serious Play™ (LSP), where participants, primarily in a business context, use LEGO® bricks to build symbolic and metaphorical models and present them to other participants [12]. The method is strongly influenced by psychological theories of learning, and calls on ideas of play, constructionism, the Hand-Mind Connection, the use of metaphors and complex adaptive systems (emergence). More recently LSP has been adopted for use in a number of educational contexts [13].

2.2 Procedure

The participants for this study attended one of two workshops – “*Indigenous Engineering: Looking at Engineering from Different Perspectives, Practices and Principles*”, and “*Shifting Perspectives – Changing Direction: Integrating Aboriginal Engineering into Modern Engineering Curricula*”. Collectively the workshops brought together 32 engineering educators from a total of eleven universities around Australia and New Zealand who were interested in exploring how they might integrate

Indigenous perspectives into the engineering curriculum. All academic levels within Schools of Engineering were represented, from Associate Dean Teaching and Learning to tutor and included one administrative staff member and three people from outside the university sector. One person was Indigenous. There was a variety of previous experience with Aboriginal people or communities.

The goal of the workshops was for participants to explore their understanding of three worldviews (Western, Engineering and Indigenous) by constructing a symbolic 'landscape', and to reflect on how this might impact engineering education. There are three phases to the method.

Phase 1: Introduction

After a brief introduction to the goal of the workshop, the guidelines were explained:

- everybody takes part and contributes to building the symbolic landscape
- there is no ONE right answer
- there is no prescribed way of laying out the landscape
- play is an essential component [14]
- trust your hands and the process
- on completion, there will be a collective exploration of the symbols/metaphors
- finally we will reflect on implications for engineering education

Participants were then asked to choose a worldview they would like to explore and to group themselves accordingly.

Phase 2: Construction

Each group was given a large sheet of brown paper, a random collection of wooden blocks, Paymobil® plastic human figures, sticky notes and pens and invited to collectively create a symbolic representation of their chosen worldview. Construction began with a short period during which time participants 'played' with the blocks and figures while listening to each other's individual understanding of the chosen worldview. As this activity proceeded discussion became more focused, and participants in each group contributed to a shared construction.

Phase 3: Participatory meaning-making and reflection

When each group had completed their symbolic construction, we all gathered at each worldview landscape in turn. Each presenting group shared the meanings they assigned to the various constructions and object placements. Then the audience shared their reactions and responses, asked questions and explored further possible symbolic and metaphoric interpretations and understandings. By this process we were able to arrive at a collective understanding of the significance of each worldview landscape.

Occasionally, an individual commented about a construction they had placed in the landscape, saying "I have no idea what this might mean", or "I don't know why I put that there". This opened up the discussion to even further exploration with other participants offering possible perspectives. This can be a critical moment in the process and, indeed, a benefit of the method, since it allows an exploration of aspects that may not be fully conscious.

To add further depth and richness to the discussions each symbolic landscape was viewed as a 'rich picture' [15] and a Jungian picture interpretation framework [16] (see *Figure 2*) was used to support meaning-making of symbolic landscape.

Figure 2. Jungian picture interpretation framework

3 RESULTS

Since the intention of this paper is to describe the symbolic constructivist methodology, only a limited analysis is presented here. A separate journal paper with a detailed analysis of the outcomes of the two workshops is in preparation.

3.1 Symbolic landscapes

Three of the symbolic landscapes constructed during one of the workshops are shown here (see Figures 3-5). Each landscape was photographed and annotations based on the final group discussions have been added to each worldview landscape to identify key individual features.

Western worldview

Figure 3. Symbolic construction of the Western worldview

Presentation of the Western worldview symbolic landscape (see *Figure 3*) began with the statement: “We have constructed all three worldviews”. The ensuing discussion explored how this might reflect an underlying philosophy that “we know everything!”, as further exemplified by the elaborate and considered construction in the ‘philosophy’ corner. This was in stark contrast to the placing of Indigenous people as an undifferentiated mass in the ‘unconscious corner’ of the landscape.

Some of the themes that emerged from the discussion are shown in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Themes emerging from exploration of the Western worldview.

Philosophy	Values
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> dominated by corporate power corporate climbing is important a dividing line between the ‘haves’ and the ‘have nots’ ‘ordinary’ people objectified with little time for relationship technical focus to problem solving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> efficiency individualism short time frame political expediency economic development exploring opportunity resource scarcity resolvable by technology
Unconscious	Nature
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> very little knowledge of Aboriginal people and Indigenous culture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> natural world is to be dominated and controlled, exploited without question little accountability for environmental impact
Centre – What is seeking conscious attention?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to bridge a corporate worldview with an Indigenous worldview? How to bridge a philosophy of materialism and corporate climbing with an accountability for environmental impact? 	

Engineering worldview

Construction of the engineering landscape (see *Figure 4*) began with participants competing to build the highest tower. A number of towers were built, toppled, and then rebuilt.

The church in the bottom right quadrant was the last construction added with the people included almost as an afterthought.

Figure 4. Symbolic construction of the engineering worldview

Some of the themes that emerged from the discussion are shown in *Table 2*.

Table 2. Themes emerging from exploration of the engineering worldview.

Philosophy	Values
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> empty, except for a scattering a wooden blocks towards the bottom of the quadrant Does engineering, as a very 'practical' discipline require a philosophy and values? Do the philosophies and values underpinning engineering need to be made conscious and articulated? 	
Unconscious	Nature
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> because engineers are at the mercy of regulatory bodies and private ('pirate') developers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – there is a sense of meeting the minimum standard – creativity is constrained 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> engineers construct buildings and infrastructure to support and 'nurture' society people added as an afterthought
Centre – What is seeking conscious attention?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> strength is important engineering can be visionary and inspirational engineers make sure that constructions are dependable 	

Indigenous worldview

It is important to note that the landscape symbolising the Indigenous worldview (see *Figure 5*) was constructed by non-Indigenous people and is therefore a Western perspective of an Indigenous worldview.

Figure 5. Symbolic construction of the Indigenous worldview

In contrast to the previous two landscapes, it was more difficult to explore the symbols of the Indigenous worldview landscape using the Jungian picture interpretation framework, which suggested that collectively our understanding of Aboriginal people and culture was difficult to frame. The participatory sense-making and reflexive discussion around this lands

cape opened up an exploration of some of the challenges of integrating a different worldview into the traditional engineering education framework.

The themes emerging from the discussions of this landscape are shown in Table 3, and are framed as questions engineering education may need to ask.

Table 3. Implications of some of the themes emerging from exploration of the Indigenous worldview.

General observations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • absence of any Playmobil® figures to represent Aboriginal people – and the difficulty this implies in developing relationships with people who are invisible • the number of question marks in the landscape – suggesting the importance of acknowledging ignorance about Aboriginal culture • the repeated placement of figures symbolising legal systems – what is the legality of sharing Indigenous knowledge? 	
Philosophy	Values
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • control by dominant culture – important to acknowledge equal sovereignty in relation to knowledge and worldview • community and focus on relationship – in contrast to focus on task 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • it is critical to acknowledge the history of Aboriginal people and the impact this has on engagement of Indigenous students in engineering • the value of Ancestral knowledge in current times
Unconscious	Nature
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • circle – circular vs linear thinking • How might engineering education acknowledge the sacred? • There is a danger that Indigenous knowledge could become a 'museum exhibit' that is not seen as relevant or accessible to engineers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • community provides nurturing and support • implications of collectivist compared with individualistic learning
Centre – What is seeking conscious attention?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aboriginal culture and worldview has much to offer engineering education • How to integrate Aboriginal pedagogies in engineering education 	

4 Discussion and impact for engineering education

This paper presents a powerful methodology that can be applied to researching attitudes, beliefs, expectations, values and understanding (and much more) in contexts ranging from curriculum design to classroom pedagogy, problem solving and scenario evaluation. Its symbolic constructivist approach catalyses and facilitates sense-making and allows non-conscious material to be brought into the light and discussed, greatly expanding the depth of exploration and richness of insight around the subject being addressed.

The application of the methodology presented here has enabled a deeper exploration with participants of complex issues around underrepresentation in engineering. In this case, the exploration of Australian Aboriginal perspectives in relation to dominant Western worldviews and traditional engineering worldviews. Departure from the more common approach of sharing thoughts through text and verbalisation of ideas gives participants the opportunity to consider and question not just the views of others, but their own. It also provides the necessary stimulus for participants to express views and consider meanings that were previously difficult to put into words. In this instance, the method highlighted the inherent challenges in integration, or even respectful acknowledgement of worldviews that are not adequately represented in engineering education (in this case Aboriginal Australian). Although initiatives aimed at greater diversity and inclusion are increasingly common in engineering education and industry, deeper analysis of unconscious values and belief systems that have resulted in current underrepresentation of particular groups is critical.

The authors believe that this methodology could prove useful as an alternative method for workshopping a range of complex issues within engineering education where unconscious values and belief systems (also termed unconscious bias) can have such significant impact on enacting positive change.

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